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Creating favorable conditions in transport systems on streets and roads

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Annotation: The streets can often be redesigned as shared spaces, with a dramatically improved environment for walking, bicycling, and playing while accommodating service, delivery, and very local motor vehicle access.

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INTRODUCTION

Many cities have primarily residential or other low-intensity streets where sidewalks and green infrastructure are either substandard or non-existent. These streets operate as de facto shared spaces, with people driving, bicycling, and walking in the roadway. Flooding and crumbling street surfaces are common. (1) (2) (3)

These streets can often be redesigned as shared spaces, with a dramatically improved environment for walking, bicycling, and playing while accommodating service, delivery, and very local motor vehicle access. (2) (4) (5)

Streets that are to operate as shared streets must be designed explicitly to promote safe, extremely low vehicle speeds. (3) (4) (7)

The roadbed accommodates low-volume local traffic. Parking occurs informally along the street and there may be unimproved drainage trenches. (5)

Pedestrians use the entire road space for walking but are not provided any formal walking space or protection from through traffic. If any operational friction occurs (such as two vehicles passing, or a moving vehicle passing a parked vehicle),

pedestrians are consigned to the edge of the street, in very uncomfortable walking conditions. (6)

The previous chapter opened by addressing the need for transport policy to be nested within a greater framework of strategic planning so that decisions made within the transport sector are coherent with general policy aims of governments at the local, regional and national levels. Such an approach entails identifying and articulating shared goals and then ensuring that appropriate linkages are made with policy objectives within the transport sector as well as outside of the transport sector to other sectors of governments as well as with the private sector.

While the international echelon is not the first one that comes to mind when thinking of governmental or quasi-governmental responsibility for addressing urban congestion, it is important in certain circumstances – most notably within the European Union. While not having a direct responsibility for transport policy or planning at the regional level, the EU does fill an important role by organising and sponsoring common research on the topic.

On the national level projects should

be prepared with a more detailed and operational focus with respect to circumstances and needs. National transport policy can be included in a general sustainable growth strategy and might contain for example a national multimodal transport investment plan or study of optimisation of the traffic system.

Within countries, regions and cities, policies should be agreed and implemented in reference to shared goals and principles. Measures that are put into place according to this shared framework for policy need not address transport directly but can focus on other sectors and/or levels of decision-making that have an influence on transport, e.g. fiscal and/or trade policy.

Within the transport sector, some measures may not act on traffic congestion directly, but may still enhance the efficiency of measures targeting transport operations or demand management. Because they can set the right framework conditions for a long-term policy to tackle traffic congestion, they should not be neglected. Among these are those measures that seek to change the fiscal treatment of travel and vehicles and those that seek to address the organisation of working hours.

The first strategic principle outlined in the previous chapter referred to the need for congestion management policies to address some of the fundamental “drivers” of congestion, and, in particular, to address the linkage between land development patterns and traffic growth

Many urban regions face the challenge of balancing growth, impacts on land use and the implications these have on traffic and congestion. Not all regions, however, face the same patterns of land use and land development. Some cities are

characterised by a mature, dense and economically powerful core that is surrounded by a growing ring of lower density development, others are formed by a network of lower density urban poles spread loosely across the whole of the urban region and yet others are characterised by a dense core and a dense and very widespread periphery. It is clear that throughout the OECD/ECMT regions, no single *form* of urban structure dominates although several similar *patterns* of urban development are shared. In this context, it makes little sense to argue that one form of urban development is inherently “better” than another with regards to congestion management objectives.

What can be said, however, is that given the link between land use patterns and traffic patterns, much should be done to ensure that congestion management strategies address the relationship between the two. A long-term strategic policy to tackle traffic congestion should then include some reference to the coordination of transport policy, urban planning and environmental goals in order to deliver sustainable outcomes. In the specific context of congestion management, some focus should be made on addressing trip generation and its management through urban planning tools. Land use can influence locations of trip generating facilities and activity patterns. Influencing demand through urban planning can therefore contribute to decreased road traffic and help to mitigate congestion.

Land-use planning includes growth management – e.g. regulation of location, density, quality and rate of development. Transport policy, on the other hand, aims to manage existing and future traffic levels that are and will be generated by shifts

in trip-making activity, itself linked to land-use decisions. Thus, in order for policy to address the upstream drivers of the traffic that is circulating on a region's roads, it is necessary to integrate traffic planning with land use planning.

Land-use strategies also embrace urban design. However, it is important to note that "preferences" for urban design patterns may vary from one region to another. Indeed, not only may preferences differ but the impact of urban development patterns may differ as well depending on the context. Communities should have the opportunity to collectively reflect on, and plan for the type of cities and urban areas they wish to live in. This means that the consultation processes identified in Chapter 11 may very well deliver different specific recommendations and objectives relating to the type of urban development communities wish to have.

IMPROVING THE RELIABILITY OF URBAN ROAD SYSTEM PERFORMANCE

Travel time reliability and more generally, the predictability of transport system performance, has often not been the explicit focus of congestion management policies in the past. Congested roads are generally unreliable roads – research conducted for TRANSFUND¹ indicates that while variability of travel times is insignificant under a volume capacity (v/c) ratio of 0.9, it increases sharply to a v/c of 1.3, where it ceases to increase further – thus much of what can be done to reduce excess congestion will also deliver travel time reliability benefits. These other measures are addressed in both the preceding and proceeding chapters, however, there are a few particular

strategies that specifically target and deliver travel time reliability improvements. These are explored in this Chapter.

Policies seeking to deliver more predictable and stable travel times on urban roads should account for the following:

- Research into travel time reliability largely supports the findings from recent traffic management and transport economics research – travel time reliability can best be delivered when traffic on the roadways is managed such that actual flows are below the roadway's physical capacity.
- Given the importance of roadway incidents in contributing to unpredictable travel times, preventing and better managing these can lead to important gains in travel time reliability.
- Research suggests that measures that increase intersection capacity can deliver trip reliability benefits without necessarily improving average travel times. Despite their limited impact on average travel times, the trip reliability benefits derived from these measures deliver tangible benefits to roadway users.
- More generally, small reductions in v/c ratios can deliver large reliability benefits – especially if these bring v/c below 1.0 – even if they do not deliver tangible travel time benefits.
- Finally, the largest benefits in travel time reliability may occur at inter-peak times. Reducing v/c from 1.1 to 0.8 at the inter-peak will have a very large impact on reliability. As well, whereas reducing v/c in highly congested peak hours from 1.0 to 0.9 will have an important impact, reducing from 1.6 to 1.3 will have almost no perceptible impact on reliability at all. This suggests that the greatest benefits

stemming from reliability-specific measures would flow to those who can re-schedule their departure times away from the highly congested peak.

The extent to which crashes, roadworks, and other incidents or unplanned events impact traffic flow varies from time of day (peak vs. off peak hours) and by type of road network (dense urban vs. uninterrupted motorway-type facilities). Losses of capacity on untravelled roads or at off peak times obviously have little impact on travellers since roads – but they can have a significant impact at peak hours in urban areas. One research report from the United States² describes the scope and scale³ of such temporary capacity losses on urban motorways and main arterials

The importance of crashes and incidents in exacerbating travel delay in the US is mirrored in many other countries as well. By their very nature, these types of incidents are unpredictable and can greatly deteriorate travel time predictability. The US study also highlights the importance of workzones which, while predictable to road managers, may be less so to road users and can thus have an impact on the stability of travel times. This chapter will examine measures that can reduce the impacts of these two factors on travel time variability within urban areas. This chapter will also examine strategies to reduce the incidence of urban freight delivery urban freight delivery on travel time predictability even though the US study seems to indicate that this was not a major issue in the US in 1999. This is because recent reviews of freight delivery impacts throughout the OECD/ECMT area have found this activity to be an

important contributor to congestion and one that is growing as e-commerce and logistics practices continue to change.

RESEARCH RESULTS

❶ Textured or permeable pavements that are flush with the curb reinforce the pedestrian-priority nature of the street. Special pavements, especially permeable interlocking concrete pavers, may be subject to additional maintenance costs and should be selected based on regional climate and long-term durability. Material selection should consider compatibility with winter maintenance, such as plowing, where applicable. If permeable pavements are used in the corridor, site facilities to minimize the amount of run-on from impervious areas.

❷ In the illustrated example, trench drains collect runoff and direct into bioretention planters, while also providing a detectable alert between the shared roadbed and parking/pedestrian access lane. Shallow gutter pans may also be appropriate for directing runoff, depending on volume. (6)

❸ Grade the street to provide accessible, level walking surface while directing stormwater flow to green or gray stormwater infrastructure. The cross slope must be at least 1% to drain runoff, but cannot exceed 2% to provide an accessible pedestrian surface.

If permeable pavement is used across the full roadway, design the street grade and cross slope to channel water that does not infiltrate down the street to an approved discharge point.

Low fencing or slotted curbs may be sited around the entire edge of bioretention facilities to prevent incursion by pedestrians or vehicles. Bioretention facilities with vertical walls should be shallow in tighter

geometries to reduce tripping and injury risk and allow for ease of maintenance.

④ Gateway treatments that slow or restrict traffic flow are critical to enforcing low-speed motor vehicle operation and provide safe and comfortable walking and bicycling conditions. Pinchpoints, speed humps, and raised crosswalks or speed tables are effective at enforcing motor vehicle speed, but must be designed to align with water flow patterns.

Street furniture, including bollards, benches, planters, and bicycle parking, can help define a shared space, subtly delineating the traveled way from the pedestrian-only space. Bioretention can integrate seating or artistic elements to further define edging, protect stormwater facilities from incursion, and enhance the sense of place.

Bioretention facilities may need to be lined, especially when in close proximities to basements and structures. Implementation may require either relocating or installing a sleeve around service utilities near bioretention facilities.

CONCLUSION

In some cases, parking may be permitted directly adjacent to properties in a residential environment. Ensure that pedestrians are provided clear accessible paths along the entire surface of the street and to destinations at all times of the day.

Figure 2. Case Study: The Street Edge Alternatives (SEA) Street Pilot

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